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Tarakanov P.Yu.

postgraduate of Saratov Chernyshevsky State University,
Russia

Evolution of the concepts of structural transformation of the national economy in the world

***Abstract.** The article examines the evolution of the features and mechanisms for the implementation of structural transformations in foreign countries, which led to the formation of the currently existing highly efficient market economies. An attempt is made to investigate the evolution of the basic theories of the cyclical development of the economy and to determine their main features in the issue of factor influence on the cyclicity and structural transformations in the system of the national economy. As a conclusion, the author substantiates an approach to determining the content of structural changes in the system of the national economy as a transition from one paradigm of development and economic growth to another paradigm more adequate to global challenges and internal demands facing society.*

***Keywords:** structural changes, national economy, government regulation, development concept, structural policy.*

At the present stage of development of the global economy, countries with a transitional type of economy face the question of the need to implement systemic transformations and change the economic models of state development. At the same time, structural changes must have a comprehensive influence to ensure the formation of a new quality of the economic system. However, the definition of such models for the implementation of systemic and structural changes requires a deep analysis of existing concepts in order to find optimal solutions that ensure the achievement of a high level of socio-economic effects.

The countries of the post-Soviet space are faced with the need to modernize the economy, and all of them, to a greater or lesser extent, experience a shortage of financial and intellectual resources for its implementation. World experience shows that modernization is carried out with the simultaneous use of national resources and foreign investments attracted to the country, new knowledge and technologies. There are two types of modernization: 1) creative (pioneering, leading), if the technological and institutional innovations developed in the country gain recognition and begin to spread around the world, bringing the country a certain rental income; 2) adaptive (imitation, catching up), carried out by introducing borrowed innovations, which is associated with certain costs for the acquisition of copyrights, patents, licenses, equipment, engineering, service maintenance, etc. (payment of innovative rent.) Creative and adaptive types modernization in countries are combined in different proportions, which reflects their economic and innovation potential [4].

At the same time, creative and adaptive types of modernization are a kind of criterion criteria, on the basis of which it is possible to analyze a number of concepts and theories that provide for the implementation of qualitative and quantitative structural changes in certain economic systems [2].

A typical example of classification according to one of the criteria is given by the model of M. Hannan and J. Freeman. They took as the initial parameter the source that encourages the organization to change. In this regard, there are three points of view on structural changes in the organization: 1) breeding theories based on natural selection and selection of socio-cultural samples; 2) balance theories (called “adaptive”), which include both passive-adaptive and actively adapted; 3) the theory of chances, in which change is described as a product of the action of many poorly controlled factors, and the results of the change are weakly correlated with both the goals of the organization and the requirements of the environment.

Some of the most widespread are the concepts (theories) of immanent development (the main ideologists are M. Kirton, S. Siegel, W. Kemmerer). According to this concept, any structure is transformed through its inherent variability property and based on its own capabilities and resources. Moreover,

external factors (the immanently transforming systems themselves) are not denied, but considered as additional. They can speed up, slow down, stop the transformation and even destroy the modified object [4].

Opposite views on the nature of the emergence of changes are offered by the externalistic exogenous concept (C. Arjiris, R. Duncan, R. Zaltman). She explains the reasons for the change to phenomena outside the enterprise. Proponents of the theory assume that the organization itself is devoid of any ability to change and without the action of external forces remains unchanged. The varieties of this theory are: behavioral theory (based on the "stimulus-response" paradigm). Without stimulus, and this is always something external to a person or an enterprise, they are not capable of any reaction (activity, transformation) and the theory of environmentalism (explains any change by factors acting outside the organization. According to this theory, it is assumed that it is forces form, control and destroy the organization) [4].

The theoretical analysis of the concepts and theories of structural reforming of economic systems of different levels made it necessary to consider in more detail the most popular of them. In particular, one of the modern and progressive basic paradigms of structural reform is the concept of sustainable development. This concept provides for an orientation towards combining and balancing the interests of business entities, consumers and society as a whole. It systematically combined three main components of sustainable development of society: economic, environmental and social.

The concept of post-industrial (information) society by D. Bell and E. Toffler is based on the progressive development of a society of a new format. Scientists assign a leading role to integrated information and communication technologies, knowledge-intensive industries and knowledge, which gradually cease to perform an auxiliary function and turn into an independent resource, on the basis of which important management decisions are made.

The first methodological foundations of the theory of the information society were formulated in the work of K. Clarke "Economics in 1960", as well as in the works of J. Fourastier "The Great Hope of the Twentieth Century": the division of

social production into three sectors. These are the agrarian (primary), industrial-industrial (secondary) and service sectors (tertiary). Also, the thesis of the dominance of the tertiary sector in conditions of economic growth was taken as an important methodological principle. These authors came to the conclusion that the growth in the importance of the service sector is realized in two aspects: in an increase in the share of this sector in the structure of the labor force, as well as in the structure of GDP. In fact, it was another of the foundations of the information society. The principle of the dominance of the technological aspects of the organization of social production over the class structure has also extended to a specific analysis of the economic development of the modern world. In the new theory, ideas began to emerge about the formation of groups of higher and lower countries in the presence of a universal path of development of lagging countries, formed by developed countries [1].

The concept of technological change (J. Schumpeter, M. Tugan-Baranovsky) is closely related to the theory of cyclical development. Innovation cycles are inextricably linked with scientific and technical investments, as well as with economic cycles, largely determining fluctuations in economic growth and reproduction efficiency. These ideas were developed by J. Schumpeter, who, insisting on the innovative nature of long cycles and determining the uniqueness of the conditions of each cycle in terms of concentration of funds, saw the main reasons for economic fluctuations in a different plane. He argued that the emergence of a group of new technologies leads to an economic boom, and this, accordingly, predetermines the saturation of the market with them. In his opinion, long waves are generated from each basic innovation and represent a large number of innovations that have an improvement in nature.

Tugan-Baranovsky M.I. noted that a characteristic feature of capitalist development is a relatively slow growth in the production of consumer goods and a rapid growth in the production of means of production. This testifies to the high activity of innovation processes in the capitalist economy in comparison with other economic systems. He also made the pioneering conclusion that it is not consumption and demand that govern production, but that production itself controls

consumption, and this happens through the accumulation of capital and its investment in new technologies and production. Indeed, as M.I. Tugan-Baranovsky noted, as technology progresses, in the production process the worker is replaced more and more by the machine, and in capital expenditures the cost of wages is each time a smaller part, while the cost of the means of production is all more. In this case, the worker in comparison with the machine recedes into the background, respectively, the market created by the consumption of the worker in comparison with the market created by the productive consumption of the means of production recedes into the background. So, according to M. Tugan-Baranovsky, NTP can provide a higher quality and continuous level of production.

In addition, the institutional theory, the author of which is the Nobel laureate Douglas North, substantiates the need to take into account the importance of the institutional environment in the implementation of structural transformations. The institutional environment is considered as a certain set of formal and informal institutions (legal norms, traditions, rules for conducting economic activities, etc.) that have an exogenous nature of influence on the behavior of economic entities.

Another important point is the introduction by institutionalists into scientific circulation of the concept of transaction costs, the role of which has increased due to structural changes in the world economy at the end of the 20th and beginning of the 21st centuries. It was during this period that there was an active movement of production facilities from highly developed countries (USA, Germany, Great Britain, France, Japan) to countries with cheap natural and human resources.

A slightly different approach to the problems of macroeconomics and economic growth is defined in the theory of economic equilibrium (D. Hicks, P. Samuelson). P. Samuelson proceeded from the fact that each area of analysis, each problem (theory of pricing, taxation system, organization of production on a national scale) is a concrete expression of the general concept. The unifying core is the idea of maximizing the result and the principle of movement to a state of equilibrium. The process of successive approximations of the economy to constant conditions generates a tendency to equalize variable conditions in accordance with

the general equilibrium conditions. The book by J. Hicks "Value and Capital" was of great theoretical importance in developing the concept of dynamic stability in general equilibrium models and deriving conditions under which an unbalanced economic system can return to a state of equilibrium.

In the revolutionary type at the regional level, one can note the concept of spatial diffusion of innovations, the author of which is the Swedish scientist Torsten Hegerstrand. He came to the conclusion that the speed of innovation diffusion does not depend on distance, but on the translational ability of individual cities through which it is carried out. In addition, T. Hegerstrand insisted primarily on the social effect of the diffusion of innovations. At the same time, as noted above, innovations can provide economic, scientific and technical, financial, resource, environmental and other types of effect. Hegerstrand not only investigated the mechanism of diffusion of innovations, but also substantiated the types of their diffusion: 1) diffusion of expansion, when an innovation spreads evenly in all directions from the source of origin; 2) diffusion of movement, that is, the spread of innovation in a certain direction; 3) mixed diffusion [6].

The evolutionary principle in building the optimal structure of the economy at the regional level was introduced by the German scientist August Lesch. He was the first scientist who proposed a theory of the location of production in a market economy, where the main role was assigned not to reducing costs (raw materials and transport), but to maximizing profits. Integrating the experience of predecessors (J. von Thünen, W. Launhardt, A. Weber, etc.), A. Lesch creates his own concept of the economic landscape, in which the determining factor is the marketing zones of enterprises of different levels, which form a network of economic regions with nodes in cities. The ideal shape of the network is hexagonal honeycomb, in reality the cells are in the form of triangles or quadrangles. Unlike similar constructions by V. Kristaller, the model proposed by A. Lesch was a model of market equilibrium, and not a planned prescription, in fact, it was a model of the territorial self-organization of society and its economic life.

Within the framework of the theory of industrial clusters, M. Porter defined the category "cluster", characterized the stages of cluster identification, formulated the main principles of state policy to promote the development of clusters, but the main value of this theory is that it considers an industrial cluster as a form of spatial organization of production. M. Porter interprets clusters as "geographically close groups of interconnected companies and associated institutions in a particular industry, linked by common technologies and skills. They usually exist in a geographic area where communications, logistics and human resources are readily available. Clusters are usually located in regions, and sometimes in a separate city. " A prerequisite for the formation of clusters is innovative technologies, and clusters are the most effective form of organizing innovative processes.

A review of the theory of industrial clusters by M. Porter and the theory of regional clusters by M. Enright showed that their authors pointed to the successful functioning of the cluster form of the territorial organization of production only if there is a powerful scientific base that provides a close relationship between science and production, and favorable conditions for the commercialization of scientific and technical knowledge [5].

The theory of "growth poles" is based on the provision that large enterprises play a fundamental role in the development of the economy of cities and surrounding areas. Being a point of accelerated development, such enterprises, together with the settlements of their localization, are called growth poles. In the writings of F. Perrault, it is indicated that such an enterprise must necessarily be industrial.

In general, for the formation of the paradigm of structural reform of the economy, we propose to select the provisions of individual concepts, taking into account the hierarchy of functional levels of the implementation of transformational changes.

Functional level hierarchy:

1. Strategic level (concept of sustainable development).
2. Project level (institutional concept; concept of technological change).

3. Operational level (the concept of production location; the concept of spatial diffusion of innovations).

An interesting is the integral concept (P. Blau, J. Pfeffer), widely used in the practice of corporate governance and is the basis for providing structural approaches to the problem of organizational development of an enterprise. The external environment is interpreted as a "target environment", that is, a set of other organizations and groups with which this organization is in direct interaction or competition. The initial parameter in the implementation of this concept is the assumption that the condition for the functioning of an organization is its interaction with certain elements of the environment, the exchange of resources. The way to ensure balance has significant differences and is expressed through: 1) the mechanism of rational, but passive adaptation of the organization to the environment (adaptation); 2) changes are deliberately and intentionally introduced by the organization into the state of the environment (adapted environments).

In addition, according to representatives of the German school of economics (Friedrich List, Wilhelm Roscher, Karl Knies), the development of the economy is based on high-quality legislation, high-tech material production and a developed social infrastructure.

In our opinion, the theorem of T. Rybczynski, a British economist of Polish origin, is important in understanding the structural transformation of the national economy. It notes that with constant relative prices for a product, an increase in the volume of one factor will lead to a more than proportional increase in production in a sector that intensively uses this factor, and an absolute decline in the production of another product.

In fact, Rybczynski's theorem is a development of the Heckscher-Ohlin theory, which substantiates international trade from the standpoint of the expediency of exporting those goods in which countries have a factor advantage and ensure high incomes. However, the experience of introducing such an approach has shown a decrease in sectoral diversification in the national economy, leading to the effect of the "Dutch disease". Therefore, in order to prevent negative consequences, it is worth

improving the legislation "on localization" in order to simultaneously remain a relatively open economy and protect domestic producers, while ensuring international industrial cooperation.

In general, in order to select the main concepts and theories that provide for the implementation of structural transformations, in our opinion, it is necessary first of all to take into account the following classification features:

- period of implementation of changes (current, prospective);
- the complexity of the changes (extended, simple);
- direction of changes (objective, subjective);
- the nature of the changes (preventive, situational, adaptive);
- the degree of change management (permanent, discrete, cyclical);
- the scale of changes (system, point);
- duration of changes (long-term, medium-term, short-term);
- type of change (evolutionary, revolutionary).

Despite the fact, in our opinion, there is no single absolutely suitable concept for the implementation of full-scale effective structural changes in the system of the national economy. Indeed, this or that concept has certain limitations (conditions for its success), and this is not always possible to ensure in reality, especially in the short term.

Therefore, today the issue of eliminating structural deformations and ensuring the balance of economic sectors is a priority task at any level of economic relations. Thus, taking into account the provisions of certain concepts should be determined both by the level of economic relations, taking into account the conditions and characteristics of the economic system, and by the strategic objectives of achieving structural optimum.

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